

Effects of Kinesiology Taping in Individual with Ankle Instability – A Literature Review

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Abstract

Ankle instability, a persistent issue often resulting from repeated sprains, can significantly diminish stability and increase the likelihood of further injury. In recent years, Kinesiology Taping (KT) has emerged as a potential non-invasive technique aimed at improving balance and stability without restricting joint mobility, making it a popular choice in rehabilitation settings. Despite its growing use, the efficacy of KT in managing ankle instability remains under debate due to variations in application techniques and the inconsistency of results across studies. This literature review seeks to assess the effectiveness of KT in alleviating ankle instability and to provide insights that could guide clinical practice while promoting better patient outcomes, particularly in reducing the risk of re-injury. The review follows PRISMA guidelines, involving a comprehensive search of randomized controlled trials published between January 2014 and July 2024 across databases such as PEDro, PubMed, and Google Scholar. To ensure the quality of the studies included, the PEDro scale was used to evaluate the risk of bias. The findings suggest that KT may contribute to improving balance and stability, though its effectiveness depends significantly on the method of application and the duration of its use. Some studies demonstrate substantial improvements with specific taping techniques, while others reveal minimal differences compared to placebo or control groups. Although further research, particularly with larger sample sizes and standardized protocols, is needed to substantiate these findings, current evidence points to KT's potential benefits. Overall, KT could serve as an effective intervention for enhancing balance and preventing further injury in individuals with ankle instability when applied correctly and for adequate durations.

Keywords: ankle instability, kinesiology taping, literature review

INTRODUCTION

Ankle instability is a long-term or chronic condition that often results from repetitive injuries such as ankle sprain. It is characterised by an individual's inability to maintain stability of the ankle joint during functional activities, which can increase the likelihood of re-injury and lead to chronic pain and prolonged disability.¹ The incidence of ankle instability is significant, with approximately 10% to 30% of the ankle-injured population progressing to chronic ankle instability, especially among physically active individuals, such as athletes.²

Management of ankle instability involves various therapeutic methods, including physical rehabilitation

programmes aimed at improving muscle strength and proprioception. Orthopaedic aids such as braces and orthoses are also often used to provide additional support to the weakened joint. In more severe cases, surgery may be required to repair damage to the ligaments.³ While these approaches have been proven effective, significant challenges related to patient compliance and the duration of therapy required may affect the healing process.

Kinesiology Taping (KT) has emerged as a promising non-invasive alternative method to address ankle instability. This technique involves applying an elastic bandage to the skin to provide additional support to the joint, improve proprioception, and reduce pain without limiting the joint's range of

motion.³ Recent research suggests that KT may contribute to improved stability and balance in individuals with ankle instability, although there is still debate regarding the most effective method of application and duration.²

This literature review aims to assess in depth the effectiveness of Kinesiology Taping (KT) in improving balance in individuals with ankle instability. By reviewing the relevant literature, it is hoped that this review will provide greater insight into the benefits of KT in the management of ankle instability and provide evidence-based recommendations for clinical practitioners.

METHOD

A. Search strategy

The systematic review involved searching journal databases like the Physiotherapy Evidence Database (PEDro) and PubMed/MEDLINE. The search strategy utilized keywords such as 'kinesiology tape' AND 'ankle instability'. The PICO set are, P: ankle instability, I: kinesiology tape, C: -, O: balance.

B. Inclusion/exclusion criteria

The inclusion criteria include: (1) Articles with randomized controlled trial (RCT) research designs; (2) Articles must be in English; (3) Articles were published in the last 10 years (January 2014 - July 2024). While the exclusion criteria include: (1) If there is the same article,

then other articles are excluded; (2) case reports, abstracts, conference proceedings, or thesis.

C. Data extraction

Data extraction was carried out by three separate reviewers (IDMAD, GMERP, and MHSN), and any discrepancies were settled through discussion. The study characteristics gathered included: (A) author information; (B) participant attributes such as age, gender, and sample size; (C) intervention dosage; and (D) outcome variables, with a focus on balance parameters.

D. Quality assessment

Risk of bias was assessed using a PEDro scale reviewed by three independent reviewers (IDMAD, GMERP, and MHSN) and any disagreements were resolved by discussion.

RESULT

A. Study selection

The initial search across two databases yielded 7 articles, of which 2 were duplicates and excluded. Applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, 5 articles were selected. Full-text access was acquired for 3 of these articles. After assessing eligibility, 2 articles were deemed suitable for inclusion. Consequently, the study utilized a total of 2 articles.

Explanation regarding study selection, described in Figure 1.

B. Methodological quality and risk of bias of reviewed studies

Explanation concerning the quality assessment in regards to the journals, described in table 1.

Table 1. Methodological quality of included studies using PEDro Scale

Study	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	Total Score
de-la-Torre-Domingo, et al., 2015	√	√	-	√	-	-	√	√	√	√	√	7/10
Lee and Lee, 2015	-	√	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	√	√	3/10

1. Eligibility criteria; 2. Random allocation; 3. Concealed allocation; 4. Baseline comparability; 5. Blind subjects; 6. Blind therapists; 7. Blind assessors; 8. Adequate follow-up; 9. Intention-to-treat analysis; 10. Between-group comparisons; 11. Point estimates and variability

C. Study characteristics

The characteristics of the summary of the study results used in this review are summarized in table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of reviewed studies describing the efficacy of kinesiology taping in individual with ankle disability

Author	Subjects	Intervention	Control/Comparison	Outcome Measure	Results
De-La-Torre-Domingo <i>et al.</i> , 2015	N=30 with chronic ankle instability. Men: 15, and women: 15. Age range: 18-28 years	KT for lateral ankle sprain. The experimental group was taped for a lateral ankle sprain with KT. Balance was assessed under the following 3 conditions: without taping, immediately after application, and after 7 days of use.	Placebo tape	Sensory Organization Test (SOT), the composite SOT score and composite SOT strategy were chosen. The partial score for SOT condition 2 and its strategy were considered as the secondary outcomes measures	No significant differences between the groups.
Lee and Lee, 2015	N= 9 male soccer players with functional ankle instability (FAI) Age range: <15	Ankle Balance Taping (ABT) with Kinesio tape	Placebo tape	Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT) and Ankle Balance Taping (ABT) Protocol	the real-ABT condition showed a statistically significant increase (p< 0.05) compared to the no- and placebo-ABT conditions

Participant characteristics

The characteristics of participants from the reviewed studies are outlined in

Table 2. A total of 39 individuals with a history of ankle instability were included in the analysis, with ages ranging from 15 to 28 years old. This demographic is commonly affected by ankle instability, particularly in active populations. The sample sizes of the studies varied, with the smallest group consisting of 9 subjects and the largest comprising 15 participants. Despite these differences, all studies focused on evaluating the effects of the interventions on individuals with similar conditions.

Intervention characteristics

The characteristics of the intervention are summarized in Table 2. All studies included in the randomized controlled trial (RCT) compared the effects of the intervention to a control group. The intervention used in these studies was KT to stabilize the ankle in individuals with ankle instability, while the control group was observed and given placebo taping.^{4,5} The duration of the intervention was one week.⁴

Outcome Measure

The studies aimed to assess the tools used to evaluate the effectiveness of Kinesio Taping (KT) in treating ankle instability across various individuals, with KT as the primary intervention and placebo tape as the control. De-La-Torre-Domingo et al. (2015) used the Sensory Organization Test (SOT) to measure balance but found no significant difference between the KT and placebo groups, indicating that other factors may contribute to balance improvements. In contrast, Lee and Lee (2015) utilized the Star Excursion Balance Test (SEBT) and Ankle Balance Training (ABT) protocols, finding that combining KT with ABT led to significant balance improvement, suggesting that specific application methods like ABT may enhance the effectiveness of KT.

Although both studies used different measurement tools to evaluate balance, the results showed that KT can

help in improving ankle stability, but with different effectiveness depending on the approach used.

DISCUSSION

This research aims to assess the effectiveness of Kinesiology Taping (KT) in enhancing balance for individuals with ankle instability. From table 2, there are two articles that have been reviewed that present various training methods, doses, and their relationship in providing beneficial effects on improving balance in those with ankle instability.

Kinesiology Taping (KT) is a non-invasive method that aims to provide additional support to the joint, improve proprioception, and reduce pain without limiting joint range of motion. Several studies have shown that KT can improve stability and balance in those with ankle instability, although its effectiveness may depend on the application technique and duration.

The study by De-La-Torre-Domingo et al. (2015) demonstrated that both KT and placebo tape could enhance balance right after application and after 7 days. Nonetheless, the absence of significant differences between the KT and placebo groups points to the possibility that other elements besides KT might be influencing the balance improvements.

In contrast, the study by Lee and Lee (2015) found that combining Ankle Balance Training (ABT) with Kinesiology Taping (KT) led to significant balance improvements compared to conditions with no ABT and placebo-ABT. This indicates that specific application methods like ABT may enhance the effectiveness of KT in improving balance for those with ankle instability.

The two studies revealed that while Kinesiology Taping (KT) can enhance balance, the effectiveness varies depending on the application method and its duration. For example, ABT combined

with KT produced more significant balance improvements compared to KT used for treating ankle lateral sprains. The duration and dosage of KT application also impact its effectiveness. According to De-La-Torre-Domingo et al. (2015), one week of KT application resulted in balance improvement, but not significantly more than placebo tape, implying that a longer application period or different approach might be needed for better results.

According to Kaminski, Needle, and Delahunt (2019), Kinesiology Taping (KT) can provide additional joint support and enhance proprioception, which is vital for balance and stability. KT can be a useful approach for improving balance in individuals with ankle instability, especially if applied correctly in terms of method and duration. Additional research is needed to establish the optimal application techniques and time frames to achieve the best results.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the literature review points to Kinesiology Taping (KT) as a potentially effective non-invasive method for improving balance in individuals with ankle instability. The effectiveness of KT, however, relies on the method of application and the duration of use. Despite one study finding no significant difference between KT and placebo tape, specific techniques like Ankle Balance Taping (ABT) have been shown to be more effective in enhancing balance. Consequently, the research hypothesis is supported, but further research is needed to determine the ideal KT application methods and durations.

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